

Elastoresistance analysis of NiTi shape memory alloys – effects of small cyclic strain along the <001> austenite direction

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Abstract

The shape memory effect of NiTi alloys is based on a reversible martensitic transformation, which can be induced by thermal and mechanical driving parameters, and has clear signatures in thermodynamic and transport properties. In this study, we present an elastoresistance analysis of a NiTi shape memory alloy with a Ni concentration of 50.7 at.%. The elastoresistance is sensitive to the complex behavior around the martensitic transformation and deep inside the martensitic phase. We observe rich phenomena, such as different kinds of hysteresis and accumulated resistance changes under cyclic strain, in different characteristic temperature regions related to the phase transformation. A first association to possible mechanisms that lead to elastoresistance effects in materials with a strain-driven phase transformation and a complex transformation-induced microstructure is discussed. Notably, both the single-domain volume properties and the microstructure affect transport properties such as the electrical resistance. Many of the elastoresistance effects related to microstructure have not been studied in detail yet. Overall, our analysis reveals the power of sensitive resistance measurements combined with uniaxial strain. Future work will help to further isolate different effects.

Keywords: Martensitic transformation, elastoresistivity characterization, twin boundary mobility, pseudoplasticity

1. Introduction

NiTi alloys show large and highly stable shape memory effects, which are today exploited in a wide range of technological applications, e.g. for medical implants/devices, actuators, valves, couplings, switches and damping elements [1–4]. The shape memory effects, one-way/two-way effects and pseudoelasticity, rely on a highly reversible martensitic transformation which can be initiated by thermal and mechanical stimuli [5, 6]. In general, the martensitic transformation has a displacive character [7, 8]. Individual atoms of the parent-phase lattice move by distances which are significantly smaller than the initial lattice parameters [9–11]. NiTi shape memory alloys (SMAs) are not only attractive for technological applications, they moreover represent a prototype material where elemental processes associated with the

martensitic and reverse transformation can be studied, as they occur in an experimentally accessible temperature range, and as – unlike to steels – the general occurrence of the transformation does not depend on cooling rates [12, 13].

The high-temperature phase austenite in NiTi SMAs has a B2 structure and thus exists with a Ni:Ti stoichiometry of 1:1 [14, 15]. Deviations from the ideal stoichiometry toward Ni-rich compositions result in a decrease of the equilibrium temperature between high- and low-temperature phase [16, 17]. This drop is caused by the formation of antisite defects which stabilize/destabilize the austenite/martensite, respectively [18]. The martensitic transition in NiTi is considered as a first-order transformation as it involves nucleation and growth, and rapid propagation of transformation fronts [19, 20]. The low-temperature phase martensite has a B19' crystal lattice [15, 21]. The formation of this phase involves two shear processes, first, a shear of the B2 basal plane (110) along the [1-10] direction, and a non-basal shear of type (001)[1-10] which establishes a monoclinic angle close to 97°. Martensitic microstructures contain an hierarchical arrangement of martensite variants and twin boundaries, which cover length scales between a few Angstrom and several 100 micrometers, depending on the initial pre-existing microstructure of the parent phase [22–24]. The formation of different martensite variants / twins allows to accommodate transformation strain and lattice incompatibilities [8, 25, 26].

On cooling, the transformation occurs between martensite start and finish temperatures, M_S and M_F , while the reverse transformation happens between A_S and A_F . The stress-free formation of B19' martensite results in the formation of self-accommodated microstructures which contain all possible types of martensite variants [23]. It is important to highlight that this microstructure is not fixed, as it can be altered by the presence of mechanical stresses/strains. During straining, favorably oriented martensite variants grow at the expense of less favorably oriented ones, and this can provide up to $\approx 10\%$ pseudoplastic strain [27, 28] which can be recovered when the material transforms back to austenite during heating. A similar type of martensitic microstructure can be obtained when the material cools down in the presence of external stresses, where favorably oriented martensite variants directly form during cooling from the high-temperature phase. A detailed analysis how external stresses affect the growth of certain martensite variants during pseudoplastic deformation, and which stresses are required for the movement of interfaces, is given in Ref. [29].

The B19' phase is not the only low-temperature phase which can occur in NiTi-based SMAs [13]. Depending on microstructure and composition, the R-phase is formed in binary NiTi with small B2 grains and special defect arrangements as well as in Fe and Co-containing compositions [30–32]. Furthermore, Cu, Pd and Pt can be added to destabilize B19' and simultaneously stabilize the B19 martensite [18, 33].

So far, resistivity measurements were conducted on NiTi-based SMAs on a large number of occasions. The technique was applied to tackle different objectives, such as to determine characteristic transformation temperatures and phase stabilities, see e.g. Refs. [30, 33–37], to analyze the propagation of macroscopic transformation fronts [38], to understand changes in electronic properties associated with the martensitic transformation [39, 40], to study martensite re-orientation processes [41, 42], to characterize defect accumulation during functional cycling [30, 36, 43–46], and to analyze effects related to hydrogen absorption in NiTi [47]. Resistance analysis was applied on coarse grain NiTi [48–50], nano-grained bulk

and thermomechanically processed alloys [36, 41, 42, 45–47], and on thin film SMAs [34, 37, 51]. The different phases which can occur in NiTi are characterized by different resistivity values [41, 42, 50]. Self-accommodated martensite has a relatively low resistivity, however, re-orientation under external stresses results in a significant increase. The resistivity of the R-phase in NiTi is higher than that of the B2 high-temperature phase. For the R-phase, effects of reorientation are negligible. Rodinò et al. [45] have generated stress/temperature/resistivity maps for NiTi wires which reflect a complex material behavior. It has been proposed that resistance reading from NiTi SMAs can be exploited in strain sensors [52, 53] and to monitor functional degradation [46].

Elastoresistance refers to the change of electrical resistance induced by strain. The effects of elastic deformation on the electrical conductivity of semiconductors have been studied since the 1950s, see e.g. Refs. [54, 55]. More recently, large elastoresistance effects were discovered in a class of metals with complex structural and magnetic phase transitions – the iron-based superconductors. A prototypical iron-based superconductor parent compound is BaFe_2As_2 , which superconducts, e.g., when Fe is partially replaced by Co. BaFe_2As_2 undergoes a tetragonal-to-orthorhombic phase transition simultaneously with an antiferromagnetic phase transition on decreasing temperature at 140 K. In the low-temperature orthorhombic/antiferromagnetic phase, the resistivity decreases with respect to the high-temperature phase. The resistivity anisotropy between the orthorhombic [100] and [010] directions in stress-detwinned single crystals has been investigated in detail, see e.g. Refs. [56, 57]. Interestingly, the elastoresistance of BaFe_2As_2 and similar compounds has been found to be large in the high-temperature tetragonal phase, when the strain is oriented along the direction that corresponds to the orthorhombic [100] or [010] direction [58]. The analysis of the temperature and chemical-substitution dependence of the elastoresistance was used intensively to study these compounds [59]. Even tiny strains such as 1×10^{-4} were found to induce clear resistance changes. In the previous works on iron-based superconductors, only linear, or linear and quadratic strain-resistance relationships have been reported [60]. Most commonly, the elastoresistance is quantified by the relative resistance change due to strain, which can be defined in the case of a linear resistance-strain relationship at any given temperature as

$$m = \frac{d(\Delta R/R_0)}{d\varepsilon}, \quad (1)$$

where ε is the strain and $\Delta R = R - R_0$ is the change of the resistance R with respect to the resistance at $\varepsilon = 0$, R_0 . The elastoresistance coefficient m can be decomposed into the strain dependence of the resistivity ρ and a geometric effect using

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \frac{\Delta \rho}{\rho_0} + \frac{\Delta l}{l_0} - \frac{\Delta A}{A_0} \quad (2)$$

so that

$$m = m_\rho + (1 + 2\nu) = m_\rho + m_{geo} \quad (3)$$

Here, l is the length of the sample along the strain direction, A is its cross-section perpendicular to it, ν is the Poisson ratio, and $m_\rho = \frac{d(\Delta \rho/\rho_0)}{d\varepsilon}$.

The objective of the present study is to investigate how martensitic transformations in NiTi-based SMAs can be characterized by elastoresistance measurements. It is not clear if high and low temperatures exhibit a different behavior and whether novel information can be obtained. This method potentially can be applied to contribute to a better understanding on fundamental aspects of martensitic transformation and on the effects of external stresses/strains on phase- and microstructure formation. The present study also aims at

identifying challenges or limitations which need to be addressed to implement elastoresistivity experiments for the analysis of martensitic transformations in SMAs.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Material and thermal analysis

In the present study, a NiTi SMA with a Ni concentration of 50.7 at.% was studied by temperature dependent elastoresistance analysis. The corresponding cast ingot with a weight of 1 kg was previously prepared by vacuum induction melting (VIM) using a furnace of Leybold Heraeus IS 1/III. Ni-Pellets (99.95 wt.%, Ampere GmbH) and Ti rods (>99.7 wt.%, E. Wagener GmbH) were melted together in a high-purity graphite crucible using the Ti-cladding technique reported in Ref. [61], which allows to minimize carbon concentrations of the resulting SMA. All details on the melting process, solidification and microstructures are documented in the literature [61–63]. The transformation behavior of the material was characterized by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using a device of TA Instruments 2920 CE. The heating and cooling rates were 10 K min^{-1} , following the ASTM standard for medical NiTi [64]. The sample for DSC testing was prepared by common metallographic preparation techniques, and its weight was close to 60 mg. All details in DSC testing and sample preparation are given elsewhere [16].

The sample for elastoresistance analysis was extracted from the NiTi ingot after homogenization/solution annealing at 850°C for 2 h followed by water quenching. A sample was cut out such that its longitudinal axis matched the [001] direction of the B2 phase. This was achieved by anticipating that the [001] direction represents the preferred crystal growth / solidification direction of B2 NiTi. Columnar grains, which reach sizes of several millimeters in cast NiTi alloys, therefore grow in the crystallographic [001] direction during directional solidification preferentially, which often is parallel to the geometric normal of the ingot-surface. Prior to cutting the sample with a Princeton scientific WS-22 precision wire saw equipped with a $50 \mu\text{m}$ wire and abrasive slurry, a suitable region with large columnar grains was identified using a two-step procedure. First, B2 grains were revealed by a metallographic macro-etching technique. Afterwards, crystal orientations were determined through texture scans, by using a Philips X'pert diffractometer equipped with a 5-axes goniometer. All details on metallographic preparation and X-ray analysis are given in Ref. [65].

2.2 Resistance and elastoresistance experiments

We employ a cryogenic strain cell, which is a recently developed method to uniaxially strain samples in a controlled manner at low temperatures [66]. Such cells are based on an arrangement of piezoelectric stacks. A sample is glued between two mounting pads which are displaced with respect to each other by action of these piezoelectric stacks. The achievable strain depends on the sample's size and stiffness and may reach up to $\sim 1\%$ both for tension and compression. Tension is defined as positive strain. These cells have previously been used to study elastoresistance, e.g., in Ref. [67].

Here, a small piece of approximately $2.5 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$, with the grain oriented along the long direction, was cut out of the NiTi ingot and polished to a thickness of $95 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. This sample was mounted into a cryogenic strain cell, model CS130 from Razorbill Instruments, see Fig. 1 (a,b). The sample was glued between the mounting pads using Devcon 5-minute epoxy with an overlap of at least 0.5 mm with the mounting pads, which ensures reliable strain transmission [66]. Cigarette paper was used to avoid electric contact between the sample and the mounting places. A strain gauge was glued to the bottom of the sample for monitoring of the sample strain. Note that we have limited pre-strain/pre-stress control. At room temperature, the pre-strain is expected to be close to zero. However, due to the differential thermal expansion of cell and sample the pre-strain is expected to grow slightly with decreasing temperature. Future work is necessary to establish a better control of pre-loading conditions. The resistance of the sample was measured with a Keithley 6221A/2182 delta-mode setup using a four-point probe method with Pt wires attached with silver paint to the top surface of the sample. All resistances are normalized to the initial value at 300 K . The setup was cooled down in a closed-cycle cryostat in a clean He atmosphere. At the different temperature steps ($320 - 290 \text{ K}$ and $230 \text{ K} - 180 \text{ K}$ in 5 K steps, and $290 \text{ K} - 230 \text{ K}$ in 2 K steps, see Fig. 1 (c)), we applied uniaxial cyclic strains to the sample, whose length is constrained by the stiff cell. A second piece with similar dimensions was cut from the NiTi ingot and used for the stress-free resistance measurements outside of the strain cell.

Figure 1: (a) Sketch of the setup to measure the elastoresistance of the $\text{Ni}_{50.7}\text{Ti}_{49.3}$ sample. The sample with a predominant $[001]$ orientation is mounted between two mounting pads using epoxy glue and contacted for electrical resistance measurements in a 4-point configuration on the top surface. A strain gauge is attached on its bottom surface. The mounting pads may be displaced using the piezoelectric stacks of the Razorbill strain cell, resulting in a controlled compressive or tensile strain of approximately 1×10^{-3} . (b) Photograph of the setup. (c-f) Overview of the experiment. Different temperatures steps are stabilized (c), (d). At each temperature step, the cyclic compressive and tensile strain is applied to the sample in a sawtooth-like manner (e) and the electrical resistance of the sample is measured simultaneously (f). Its resistance change due to temperature and strain variation is clearly resolved.

3. Results

Figure 2 shows the characterization of the transformation behavior of our material in the stress-free state using thermal analysis / DSC, Fig. 2(a), and resistance, Fig. 2(b,c). Figure 2 (b,c) shows data from the initial cooling (labelled '1'), subsequent heating (labelled '2') and the following cooling (labelled '3') with heating and cooling rates between 1-2 K/min. The martensitic transition is well defined both in DSC and resistance data. We determine $M_S = 282$ K, $M_F = 255$ K, $A_S = 281$ K and $A_F = 313$ K from the DSC data using the tangent method, Fig. 2(a). These temperatures correspond well to the characteristic features in the resistance data, Fig. 2(b). Overall, the resistance of the B2 phase is higher than the resistance of the B19' phase. The temperature derivative dR/dT in the B2 phase is much lower than in the B19' phase. On cooling, the resistance of the B2 phase starts to increase slightly above M_S , and it shows a sharp increase by $\sim 7\%$ close to the midpoint of the transition, and then decreases on cooling into the martensite phase. This behavior is similar on heating, but the features around the transition are less pronounced. The resistance increased slightly in value after this first stress-free temperature cycle. However, as the temperature derivative in Fig. 2(c) shows, this change amounts only to a constant offset.

Figure 2: Characterization of the transformation behavior of our $\text{Ni}_{50.7}\text{Ti}_{49.3}$ sample in the stress-free state using (a) thermal analysis / DSC and (b) electrical resistance with current along the $\langle 001 \rangle$ austenite direction. The first cooling ('1'), subsequent heating ('2') and the following cooling curve ('3') are shown and marked by the numbered arrows. (c) Temperature derivative of the data in (b). Vertical lines mark the characteristic temperatures M_s , M_f , A_s , and A_f as determined from the DSC data using the tangent method.

Figure 3 presents the elasto-resistance data of the $\text{Ni}_{50.7}\text{Ti}_{49.3}$ SMA with uniaxial strain along the $[001]$ direction. An overview in Figs. 3(a,b) shows the resistance data during the elasto-resistance measurement as a function of temperature. At each temperature step, cyclic strain is applied, which leads to a variation of the resistance that appears as a small vertical bar in this diagram. The overall resistance variation due to the applied strain is small as compared to the temperature-related variation between 180 K and 320 K. The right-hand axes show the corresponding DSC data from Fig. 2(a) for reference.

Figures 3 (c-f) show the resistance-strain curves at each temperature step. From their behavior, different characteristic regions I-VIII are identified and marked by different colors. Figure 4 shows the cyclic strain dependence of the resistance at selected temperatures within the different characteristic regions and Figure 5 shows characteristic parameters of different hysteretic features, as defined in Fig. 4(f).

Figure 3: Resistance variation of the $\text{Ni}_{50.7}\text{Ti}_{49.3}$ sample due to temperature and strain variation. (a) Overview of the resistance variation on cooling, when the strain is varied at each temperature step so that the strain-dependence of the resistance appears as a vertical bar. Different characteristic regions I-V are color coded. (b) Overview of the resistance variation on warming, when the strain is varied at each temperature step. Characteristic regions V-VIII are color coded. The right-hand scale in (a,b) shows the corresponding DSC data from Fig. 2(a) for reference, with the dashed lines indicating a smooth background. (c-f) Resistance as a function of strain at the different temperature steps.

In the high-temperature region I (320 - 295 K, cooling), the resistance depends overall linearly on strain with a slope of $m \approx 5$. With a Poisson's ratio of $\nu=0.4$, this means that the strain dependence of the resistivity amounts to $m_\rho \approx 3.2$, see equ. (3). The resistance and its strain dependence are practically temperature independent.

In region II (290-268 K, cooling), the resistance starts to increase significantly on cooling. The resistance-strain curves are still approximately linear, and their average slope is practically temperature independent with the same value of $m \approx 5$. However, as shown more clearly in Fig. 4(b), the curves show a tiny hysteresis around zero strain.

The characteristic temperature region III (266-232 K, cooling) spans the martensitic transition, which is dominated by a large positive temperature dependence of the resistance, $dR/dT > 0$. Here, the resistance changes induced by cyclic straining accumulate, such that the resistance does not reach its original value after a strain cycle, in contrast to the behavior in characteristic regions I and II. The two curves at $T = 266$ K and $T = 264$ K are an exception. They are, however, also still in the region where $dR/dT < 0$.

This accumulative behavior upon strain cycling disappears in region IV (230-200 K, cooling) deep within the martensitic phase. The average strain dependence of the resistance is $m \approx 1.8$, much smaller than in regions I and II, and close to the expected geometric effect only. Remarkably, very tiny sharp hysteretic jumps are observed in the small strain range, which are due to their size best seen in a single strain cycle [see inset in Fig. 4(d)].

A new feature appears for the lowest temperatures in the characteristic region V (200-180 K, cooling and 180-205 K, warming). A very clear and reproducible hysteresis, with five times larger resistance jumps $\Delta R_{max}/R(300\text{ K})$ than in region VI emerges first at 200 K on cooling. The hysteresis strain width $\Delta \epsilon$ amounts to 2×10^{-4} and its strain midpoint ϵ_{mid} it is found on the tensile-strain side at 200 K. This position gradually shifts to the compressive strain side on lowering the temperature to 180 K. On warming from 180 K to 205 K, the position of this hysteresis shifts again gradually to the tensile strain region.

On warming between 210 K-260 K (characteristic region VI), various other tiny hysteretic features are observed, see Fig. 4 (f,g) for examples. At most temperatures, indeed, multiple small hysteretic features are seen in the strain range $\pm 0.1\%$.

These hysteretic features disappear in the characteristic region VII (262-280 K, warming). In this region, the resistance changes upon strain cycling accumulate, similar to region III, so that the overall resistance increases with cyclic straining. However, this change is significantly less pronounced than in region III, which was part of the cooling [see Fig. 4(e), Fig. 6].

Interestingly, a large hysteretic feature appears again in region VIII (282-315 K, warming). At some of the temperatures, the width of this hysteretic features changes with each strain cycle. However, the overall resistance does not change after the multiple strain cycles. 315 K is the highest temperature for which data could be obtained. It is expected that the sample

enters the regime of a simple linear strain-resistance relationship (region I) again at sufficiently high temperatures.

Figure 5 shows details of the various identified hysteretic features, such as the maximum resistance difference $\Delta R_{max}/R(300 K)$, the strain width $\Delta \varepsilon$ and the strain midpoint ε_{mid} , defined in Fig. 4 (f). In region I (above M_S) and IV (well below M_F), all hysteresis parameters are approximately temperature independent. $\Delta R_{max}/R(300 K)$ is very small with only $\sim 5 \times 10^{-4}$ and $\sim 7 \times 10^{-4}$, respectively. The hysteresis midpoint is close to zero strain. The hysteresis in the low-temperature region V has a much larger $\Delta R_{max}/R(300 K)$ with 30×10^{-4} . It is the only feature whose position is strongly temperature dependent. This feature disappears on warming to higher temperatures. While still well below A_S , multiple hysteresis features are seen in region VI, with a small $\Delta R_{max}/R(300 K)$ of less than 10×10^{-4} , different midpoints and widths that generally increase on increasing temperature. Region VIII, above A_S , shows another type of hysteretic feature, which is again relatively large.

Figure 6 presents a more detailed analysis of the accumulated strain changes after six strain cycles. On cooling, a significant accumulated resistance change is observed only in region III. This change is mostly negative. In the most pronounced case, the resistance has decreased by 2% after the six strain cycles. The effect diminishes deep inside the martensitic phase. On warming, there is also a temperature range with noticeable accumulated resistance change after cycling straining. Here, the resistance shows an overall increase. However, the effect is confined to a smaller temperature region (region VII), and it is only half as large as on cooling.

Figure 4: Resistance variation as a function of strain at selected temperatures in characteristic regions I-VIII. (a) High-temperature region I with an almost linear elastoresistance. The linear trend is indicated by a red dotted line and has a slope of $m \approx 5$. Subtracting the expected geometric effect (equ. (3)), we find $m_\rho \approx 3.2$, indicated by the black dashed line. (b) In region II, a tiny hysteretic feature appears. (c) In region III, the resistance changes due to cyclic strains accumulate. (d) In the low-temperature region IV, the resistance change shows a small hysteresis, that is well visible in the inset, where an individual strain cycle is displayed. (e) In the low-temperature region V, the most prominent hysteretic feature is observed. (f) Definition of the parameters describing the hysteretic features, the resistance jump $\Delta R_{max}/R$ (300 K), the strain midpoint ε_{mid} and the hysteresis width $\Delta\varepsilon$. (g,h) In region VI, multiple clear hysteretic features appear. (i) In region VII, an accumulative resistance change under cyclic strain appears again and no hysteretic features can be resolved. (j) In region VIII, a pronounced hysteretic behavior is again visible.

Figure 5: Parameters characterizing the different hysteretic features as defined in Fig. 4(f) on cooling [panels (a,c,d)] and warming [panels (b,d,f)]. (a,b) Maximum resistance difference $\Delta R_{max}/R(300\text{ K})$, (c,d) strain midpoint ε_{mid} , (e,f) strain width $\Delta\varepsilon$. Different hysteretic features are identified by different symbols. The temperature regions in which hysteretic features are identified are indicated in the top panels. No hystereses could be resolved or quantified in regions III and VII.

Figure 6: Temperature dependence of the accumulated resistance changes resulting from 6 strain cycles $(R_{end}-R_{start})/R(300\text{ K})$, defined in the inset in (a), as a function of temperature on (a) cooling and (b) heating. The insets show examples of the resistance change under cycling straining.

4. Discussion

3.1 Resistivity changes and phase transformations in NiTi

Fig. 2 demonstrates that both DSC and $R(T)$ analyses reveal a well-defined transformation behavior. In principle, comparable data have been published in the literature, e.g. in Refs. [48, 62]. During cooling from the high temperature phase, the slope of the resistance curve increases when approaching the M_s temperature, Fig. 2(b). This behavior is related to changes in electronic transport which are preceding the martensitic transformation, however, the observed phenomenon is not fully understood. In this temperature range, a significant decrease of elastic constants occurs, which lowers the barrier for the shear processes associated with changes in crystal structure [68]. In the same temperature range, Katsuyama et al. [69] reported anomalous increase of positron annihilation lifetime, indicating higher defect concentrations, prior to the transformation from B2 to B19'. The observed evolution of resistivity, including the strong increase after passing the M_s temperature determined by DSC do not represent a general feature of martensitic transformation in NiTi. Resistance data published by Kunzmann et al. [48] reveal a composition dependence. In fact, the behavior documented in Fig. 2 is absent for NiTi with ideal stoichiometry [35, 40, 48, 70] or appears with weak intensity [49]. In the Kunzmann study [48], it was observed that the resistivity peak on cooling first appears for a NiTi alloy with 50.3 at.% Ni. The change in slope during cooling emanates when reaching 50.6 at.% Ni. Both features become more prominent when the Ni concentration increases further. In other publications, a similar observation has been attributed to the formation of the R phase [41, 71], however, this appears unlikely for the solutionized and quenched material considered in the present work.

One important feature shown in Fig. 1(b) is that the $R(T)$ loop does not close after completing the cooling/heating cycle where the material transforms to martensite and again to the parent phase. The fact that the temperature derivatives of the two cooling curves in Fig. 1(c) overlap shows that a constant resistance offset occurred. This behavior is likely caused by the formation of defects which were introduced into the microstructure during phase transformations due to the limited lattice compatibility between austenite and martensite, e.g. Refs. [70, 72]. The corresponding behavior was not reported in other studies where NiTi SMAs with nanocrystalline B2 microstructure were considered, e.g. Ref. [41], as these materials are more resilient to defect formation [73]. Schmelter et al. [46] have recently shown how resistivity increases during the complete service lives of NiTi SMA during iso-stress thermal cycling. It was observed that resistance data can be used to monitor fatigue damage evolution as cyclic defect accumulation yields an increase of the resistance.

4.2 Elasto-resistance

A general consideration for the elasto-resistance of shape memory alloys:

Resistance is a transport property and can therefore sense additional effects as compared to thermodynamic probes such as DSC. Namely, the resistance is determined not only by the intrinsic bulk resistivity within a single area, which is intrinsically anisotropic – especially in a low-symmetry phase – but also by the microstructure, including grain boundaries, phase boundaries and twin boundaries. Under strain, all these elements are modified, which can in principle result in a complex elasto-resistance signal.

In a conventional material with linear-elastic mechanical behavior, the application of an external strain causes mechanical stress and a widening/compression of the crystal lattice, which results in a change of the resistance. In general, there are two effects, see equ. (3): first, the geometric effect due to the elongation and transverse contraction of the sample results in a resistance change $m_{geo}=1+2\nu$, and second, the modification of the resistivity of the material m_ρ , which can e.g. result from a modification of charge carrier densities or scattering rates by strain. In SMAs, however, the situation differs due to additional mechanisms, listed below, which contribute to the overall resistance / elasto-resistance:

Mechanism A: There are elemental processes in SMAs which can limit or reduce elastic strains in the crystal lattice: During macroscopic straining (where the *total* length of a sample changes), the increase of the true elastic *local* strain can be reduced by the formation of martensite when stresses are sufficiently high to promote the formation of favorably oriented martensite variants. A similar effect results from pseudoplastic deformation in the martensitic state, when the initial martensite microstructure is altered by detwinning / reorientation, where interface migration promotes the growth of favorably oriented martensite variants. Both processes reduce the overall elastic strain but change the sample's microstructure, thus affecting the resistance / elasto-resistance behavior.

Mechanism B: The growth of favorably oriented martensite variants (e.g., during pseudoplastic deformation) alters the crystallographic texture of the martensite [74]. It is reasonable to assume that martensite single crystals not only have an elastic [75], but also an

electronic transport anisotropy. Therefore, changes in the spread of martensite crystal orientation will affect the charge transport in specific geometric directions of the material.

Mechanism C: Pseudoplastic deformation not only alters the martensite texture. It additionally affects the density of interfaces between variants [76]. At present, it is not clear whether / how internal interfaces affect resistivity in NiTi. For other systems, e.g., WO_x , special transport properties of twin interface regions have been suggested in literature [77–79].

Mechanism D: Martensite and austenite have different resistivities, Fig. 2(a). As the transformation occurs within a certain temperature range, both phases can coexist separated by phase boundaries. This coexistence will affect the overall resistance based on phase volume fractions which depend on temperatures and stresses.

Mechanism E: Martensite / austenite interface arrangements potentially affect the electronic transport. Hosseinzadeh et al. [80] have recently demonstrated that high local stresses can evolve at the austenite/martensite interface, depending on crystallographic misfit. In the case of NiTi, these stresses can fall into a range between 2 to 3 GPa, which one can expect to affect the bulk electrical resistivity near these interfaces.

Against this background, it is clear that there is a need to further investigate the potential contributions of the mechanisms described above. Especially anisotropy and interfaces are of particular interest. It has been demonstrated by Pelegrina et al. [41] that martensite reorientation, which potentially occurs during cyclic straining, significantly alters electrical resistivity. However, it is not clear at present whether the observed effect is related to crystal anisotropy / texture changes or to local electronic transport in martensite interface regions.

The elastoresistance data obtained in the present work provide a wide palette of results, which can be interpreted in the light of potential mechanisms discussed above. The findings documented in Figs. 3-6 suggest that different regimes exist where small cyclic strains affect the resistance of the SMA in different ways. The specific features observed in the different regimes are discussed as follows:

Regime I (295 K < T, cooling; high-temperature austenite phase): A linear dependence of the resistance in strain is observed, Fig. 4(a). The slope is close to 5, which is similar to $BaFe_2As_2$ around room temperature [58]. The elastoresistance is composed of a geometric and an intrinsic effect, equ. (3). With an approximated Poisson ratio of 0.4, the geometric effect is estimated to be 1.8. Thus, we find that the strain dependence of the resistivity of the austenite is close to $m_p=3.2$.

Regime II: (290 K < T < 268 K, cooling; large fraction of austenite / small fraction of martensite, but increasing during cooling): A small hysteresis occurs during cyclic straining, Fig. 4(b). One may intuitively assume that this feature indicates a small-scale transformation event where stress/strain-assisted martensite forms during loading, and which transforms back when loading conditions are reverted. However, corresponding temperatures are significantly lower than A_F (under stress-free conditions), and, therefore, it is unlikely that small martensite regions would be able to completely transform back and close the hysteresis loops. Another potential explanation for the observed behavior could be that a

small amount of martensite has already formed, e.g., in regions like B2 grain boundaries or at interfaces to inclusions which act as stress-raisers and simultaneously lower martensite nucleation barriers. However, this martensite does not form and dissolve during strain cycling. It is more likely that mechanical cycling results in a cyclic motion of interfaces, such as austenite / martensite interfaces or twin boundaries within martensite clusters (mechanisms A and B/C) on a small length scale. A third explanation could be the cyclic formation and dissolution of R-phase. However, it again seems unlikely that this phase will form in the type of material and during the loading conditions considered in the present study.

Region III (266 K < T < 232 K, cooling; large martensite volume fraction; still regions with austenite present): The DSC and resistance data in Figs. 2(a,b) (and Figs. 3(a,b)) suggest that, in contrast to regions II, a large fraction of martensite and only a small fraction of austenite is present. The amount of austenite further decreases during cooling to lower temperatures, as indicated by the softly decaying signal of the heat flow curve in the bottom of Fig. 3(a). The accumulative behavior during strain cycling, which is characteristic for regime III, Fig. 4(c) and Fig. 6(a), suggest that the cyclic load changes result in successive evolution of the microstructure. As the resistivity of martensite is lower than that of austenite (which can be extrapolated from the data in Fig. 3(b)), the observed behavior could be related to a successive accumulation of martensite during cyclic straining. As this phenomenon occurs at temperatures significantly lower than A_F , the cyclically formed martensite does not transform back to austenite. This potential cyclic accumulation of martensite therefore may result in the accumulative evolution of resistance shown in Figs. 4(c) and 6(a). The overall behavior is therefore caused by the motion of martensite/austenite interfaces (mechanism D), as both phases co-exist in the corresponding temperature range.

Regions IV and VI (230 K < T < 200 K, cooling and 210 K < T < 260 K; single phase regime / low temperature phase): In this temperature regime, small hystereses occurs during cyclic straining, Fig. 4(d,h,g). It is reasonable to assume that the corresponding resistance changes are caused by martensite twin boundary motion (mechanisms B and C). Although strain amplitudes applied in the present work are relatively small, twin boundary motion can already occur presumably in small scale sample regions [81, 82]. We expect that the observed effect will appear even stronger, when larger strain amplitudes are applied.

Region V (200 K < T, cooling and 205 K < T, warming; martensite): In the lowest temperature region considered in the present work, the occurrence of larger resistance hystereses was observed, which unexpectedly showed a pronounced temperature dependence of their strain midpoint, Figs. 4(e) and 5(d). This observation could again be related to twin boundary motion, however, this does not explain why the strain midpoint is temperature-dependent. Further work is required to verify and to rationalize this phenomenon.

Region VII (262 K < T < 280 K, warming, martensite and small fractions of austenite at elevated temperatures): This region appears to have a similar accumulative character as previously observed for region III on cooling, Figs. 4(c), (i). In both cases, martensite represents the dominating phase, whereas a small fraction of austenite is present. Cyclic straining in region VII may again affect phase volume fractions in an accumulative manner as previously discussed for region III.

Region VIII ($282\text{ K} < T < 315\text{ K}$, warming; co-existence of martensite and austenite): Most parts of the material transform from martensite to austenite during heating, Fig. 2. The resistivity hystereses associated with cyclic straining, Fig. 4(j), are likely caused by a back-and-forth movement of interfaces, similar to what has been previously suggested for regime II, Fig. 4(b).

4.3 Outlook

The present study demonstrates that elastoresistivity analysis represents an attractive method which allows to characterize elemental processes of martensitic transformations in SMAs. The full potential of this approach is not completely uncovered. The observed resistance changes can be interpreted on the basis of elementary processes associated with phase transformation events and pseudoplastic / pseudoelastic deformation processes. However, not all observations presented in this study can be satisfactorily rationalized without further analysis. Therefore, it would be required to couple elastoresistivity experiment with in-situ diffraction and microscopy experiments to gain supportive information. It is also required to extend the current experimental setup to provide an enhanced control of mechanical boundary conditions, to reach higher pre-stresses/strains, and to retrieve precise stress data during thermo-mechanical cycling.

There also is a need to further rationalize why changes in the martensitic microstructure affect the electrical resistivity by untangling the different phenomena. It needs to be understood if/how both electronic anisotropy and charge transport in interface regions contribute to macroscopic resistivity changes observed in the present study and reported in literature, e.g. Refs. [41, 45]. It is also interesting to analyze how far the observed phenomena depend on the crystallographic orientation of the B2 phase. In the present study, the sample was loaded along the [001] direction, which simultaneously corresponds to the direction of charge transport. It would be interesting to investigate the change of electrical resistance in different directions with respect to the loading direction, in order to assess potential effects related to anisotropy.

The different elastoresistivity properties in the different regions could also be exploited for sensing in technical applications. The occurrence of different patterns of resistance change during loading/unloading allows to detect whether the material is in the austenitic state, whether it currently undergoes phase transformations, or whether it is in the martensitic state. Small resistance jumps during small load changes indicate the motion of martensite interfaces. In principle, this information could be retrieved, for example, from electrically-activated actuators which are subjected to non-monotonic loading conditions. In other cases, the build-up of mechanical stresses, for example in a small gripper-device, could be detected by exploiting the linear correlation between strain and resistance in the high temperature phase.

5. Summary and conclusions

Phase transformation processes and microstructural evolution of the martensitic transition in a NiTi shape memory alloy were investigated using elastoresistance analysis for the first time. Clearly different behavior in the austenite and martensite phases, and within the phase transformation region were observed. We found the following highlights:

- 1) The resistance of austenite NiTi is sensitive to uniaxial strain along the $\langle 001 \rangle$ direction and the resistance changes linearly with a rate of change of $\frac{d(\Delta R/R_0)}{d\varepsilon} = 5$.
- 2) Different characteristic temperature regimes can be identified from the qualitatively different resistance changes induced by cyclic strain.
- 3) The elasto-resistance behavior can overall be rationalized based on elemental processes related to the phase transformation.
- 4) A strain-induced change of resistance can be related to the displacement of austenite-martensite phase boundaries and martensite-martensite twin boundaries.
- 5) When both austenite and martensite are present, the displacement of phase boundaries induced by cyclic strain can result in an accumulated resistance change of up to 2% for six strain cycles.
- 6) At the lowest temperatures, the displacement of twin boundaries (pseudoplastic deformation) by small strains causes clear resistance changes. In particular, the rearrangement of twin boundaries results in a decrease of local elastic strain with reproducible consequences in electronic transport.
- 7) Resistivity analysis during cyclic straining at constant temperature allows to detect whether the SMA is in the austenitic state, the martensitic state, or within the transition interval.

6. Data availability

To be announced.

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